

Parenting Styles and Involvement in Relation to Grade 1 Learners' Academic Performance In Selected Elementary Schools A Basis for A Partnership Program

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Publication Date: May 6, 2026

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20055096](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20055096)

Abstract

This study assessed the parenting styles and parental involvement among parents of Grade 1 learners in selected elementary schools of Amulung West District for the School Year 2024-2025, aiming to inform the development of a partnership program. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, data were collected from 135 parent respondents through questionnaires covering demographic profiles, parenting styles, and levels of parental involvement, as well as the academic performance of their children. The findings revealed that the authoritative parenting style was most prevalent among respondents. Parents reported consistently high involvement across all domains, including parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and community collaboration. Most learners achieved outstanding academic performance. Significant correlations were found between parenting styles and the variables of age, civil status, and highest educational attainment, while decision-making was significantly associated with marital status, and communication with occupation. Parenting style was also correlated with learners' academic performance, but no significant relationship was observed between parental involvement and academic outcomes. Issues and concerns regarding parenting were seldom encountered by parents. The study concludes that strong parental involvement and authoritative parenting contribute to positive educational outcomes and recommends the establishment of structured partnership programs to further enhance collaboration between parents and schools.

Keywords: *academic performance, authoritative parenting, parental involvement, parenting styles, partnership program, elementary education*

I. INTRODUCTION

The primary years are the formative years of each child. This is the level where children develop all the different aspects of growth and development. It is the stage where the child learns what he or she will become. With young learners, there are many good and bad experiences. Expectedly, young learners exhibit different kinds of attitudes. They display various behaviors that teachers, parents, and caregivers can hardly understand. At this level, they seek more attention from their parents by exhibiting unfavorable attitudes. Some of them throw tantrums if they cannot get what they want. Some of them display attitudes that are not appropriate for their age, such as yelling at classmates or playmates, hurting classmates or playmates, and using inappropriate language. Right from infancy, children learn and acquire traits and behaviors that they exhibit throughout their lifetime. There is a strong consensus that parents play a very significant role in how their children develop and function. Many of the skills children acquire are fundamentally dependent on their interactions with caregivers and the broader social environment. The quality of parenting a child receives is considered the strongest potentially modifiable risk factor that contributes to the development of behavioral and emotional problems among children. Parent-child interactions affect many different areas of development, including self-esteem, academic achievement, cognitive development, and behavior.

During socialization, parents and other authoritative figures endeavor to form children in such a way as to help them acquire worthwhile virtues cherished by society. Parents customarily are obligated to play this all-important role of socializing their children into their social milieu as primary agents of socialization. They are expected to become an important influence on the emotional, cognitive, and social development of children (Hughes, Kroehler & Zanden, 1999). It is believed that some roles are better performed by parents, which children tend to accept more readily than from any other person in their lives. Since parental roles are essentially formative, their influence on the socialization of children cannot be over-emphasized. Most studies on parenting styles have emphasized that the kind of parenting style adopted by parents has a monumental impact on children's attitudes, academic achievement, and career choices (Maccoby & Martin, 1983; Mandara, 2006).

Truly, change is the only constant, particularly in the Department of Education. The department is committed to ensuring the delivery of education in line with the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan. Education must continue to give hope and stability, contribute to the normalization of activities in the country, facilitate learners' development, and bring normalcy to their lives, but the health and safety of learners and school personnel are of utmost importance and must be protected at all times (DepEd Order No. 12, series 2020).

With the new approach to teaching in the Department of Education, problems and challenges are everywhere. Parents have faced the biggest challenges, particularly those whose children are at the primary grade level. With the new learning approach of the Department of Education, parental involvement plays a vital role in the education of their children. Parents or guardians are the best partners of schools in helping young learners learn and adapt. Parents have the biggest role in imparting knowledge to their children. They are expected to give their best in teaching their children.

As in other countries, in the Philippines, public or private schools have a PTA or Parent-Teacher Association. It is guided by Department of Education Memorandum No. 74, series of 1999. Every PTA provides mechanisms to ensure proper coordination with members of the community, provides an avenue for discussing relevant concerns, and offers assistance and support to the school for the promotion of their common interest. Regular meetings are conducted with local government units, civic organizations, and other stakeholders to foster unity and cooperation. As an organization operating in the school, the PTA adheres to all existing policies and implementing guidelines of the Department of Education. The PTA serves as a support group and as a significant partner of the school, with a relationship defined by cooperative and open dialogue to promote the welfare of the students.

Another program held by the Department of Education is *Brigada Eskwela*. It is an annual program that brings together nationwide voluntary efforts of different stakeholders. Parents, teachers, and other members of the community where a public school is located help one another with the school's maintenance and beautification every two weeks before the official start of classes. It started in 1998 upon the implementation of Republic Act 8525 or the Adopt a School Program (ASP). Its mission is to practice shared governance, bring the spirit of education to the community level, and utilize local resources to improve public schools (www.deped.gov.ph).

The family in the Philippines is perceived as an important part of society. It has been shaped by the unique history, values, experiences, adaptations, and ways of being that characterize the Filipino people and their culture (Alampay, n.d.). Coupled with the long history of political and social strife, it would seem that Filipino parents face insurmountable challenges in raising their children (Blair, 2014).

However, parenting style is a psychological construct representing standard strategies that parents use in their child-rearing. The quality of parenting can be more essential than the quantity of time spent with the child. For instance, a parent can spend an entire afternoon with his or her child, yet may be engaging in a different activity and not demonstrating enough interest toward the child. Parenting styles are the representation of how parents respond to and make demands of their children. Parenting practices are specific behaviors, while parenting styles represent broader patterns of parenting practices. Early research in parenting and child development found that parents who provide their children with proper nurture, independence, and firm control have children who appear to have higher levels of competence and are socially skilled and proficient. Additional developmental skills result from positive parenting styles, including maintaining a close relationship with others, being self-reliant, and being independent. During the mid-1980s, researchers began to explore how specific parenting styles influence a child's later development. Baumrind believed that parents should be neither punitive nor aloof. Rather, they should develop rules for their children and be affectionate with them. These parenting styles are meant to describe normal variations in parenting, not deviant parenting, such as might be observed in abusive homes. In addition, parenting stress can often cause changes in parental behavior such as inconsistency, increased negative communication, decreased monitoring and/or supervision, setting vague rules or limits on behavior, being more reactive and less proactive, and engaging in increasingly harsh disciplinary behaviors.

There are four types of parenting styles. Authoritative parents are demanding and responsive. Authoritative parenting is characterized by a child-centered approach that holds high expectations of maturity. Authoritative parents can understand how their children are feeling and teach them how to regulate their feelings. Even with high expectations of maturity, authoritative parents are usually forgiving of any possible shortcomings. They often help their children to find appropriate outlets to solve problems. Authoritative parents encourage children to be independent but still place limits on their actions. Extensive verbal give-and-take is not refused, and parents try to be warm and nurturing toward the child. Authoritative parents are not usually as controlling as authoritarian parents, allowing the child to explore more freely, thus enabling them to make their own decisions based on their reasoning. Often, authoritative parents produce children who are more independent and self-reliant. Authoritative parents set clear standards for their children, monitor the limits that they set, and also allow children to develop autonomy. They also expect mature, independent, and age-appropriate behavior from children. Punishments for misbehavior are measured and consistent, not arbitrary or violent. Often behaviors are not punished, but the natural consequences of the child's actions are explored and discussed, allowing the child to see that the behavior is inappropriate and should not be repeated, rather than not repeated merely to avoid adverse consequences. However, when punishing a child, the parent explains his or her motive for the punishment. Children are more likely to respond to authoritative parenting punishment because it is reasonable and fair. A child knows why they are being punished because an authoritative parent makes the reasons known. As a result, children of authoritative parents are more likely to be successful, well-liked by those around them, generous, and capable of self-determination.

On the other hand, authoritarian parents tend to set high standards and guidelines, and obedience is required. Authoritarian parents equate love with success and are not as nurturing as the other two styles of parenting. The parent is demanding but not responsive. Authoritarian parenting is a restrictive, punishment-heavy parenting style in which parents make their children follow their directions with little to no explanation or feedback and focus on the children and family's perception and status. Corporal punishment, such as spanking and shouting, are forms of discipline frequently preferred by authoritarian parents. The goal of this style, at least when well-intentioned, is to teach the child to behave, survive, and thrive as an adult in a harsh and unforgiving society by preparing the child for negative responses such as anger and aggression that the child will face if his or her behavior is inappropriate. Children raised using this type of parenting may have less social competence because the parent generally tells the child what to do instead of allowing the child to choose by himself or herself, making the child appear to excel in the short term but limiting development in ways that are increasingly revealed as supervision and opportunities for direct parental control decline.

Furthermore, permissive or indulgent parents have little or no expectations for their children. They often view their children as friends and have few limits imposed. The parent is responsive but not demanding. Permissive parenting is a style in which parents are very involved with their children but place few demands or controls on them. Parents are nurturing and accepting, and are responsive to the child's needs and wishes. Indulgent parents do not require children to regulate themselves or behave appropriately. The expectations of the child are very low, and there is little discipline. Permissive parents also allow children to make their own

decisions, giving them advice as a friend would. This type of parenting is very lax, with few punishments or rules. Permissive parents also tend to give their children whatever they want and hope that they are appreciated for their accommodating style. Other permissive parents compensate for what they missed as children, and as a result, give their children both the freedom and materials that they lacked in their childhood.

Additionally, uninvolved parents fulfill their children's physical needs but are otherwise distant, detached, and disengaged. Uninvolved parents may lead "full" lives, but their lives are emotionally separate from their children. There are few demands and limits, and communication and responsiveness are low. Children with uninvolved parents are likely to struggle with self-esteem issues. They tend to perform poorly in school. They also exhibit frequent behavior problems and rank low in happiness.

Parenting is one of the complex tasks every parent hopes to succeed in. For all social and educational development, the family and parenting style play an important role. Moreover, parenting forms the basis of a family environment because, without parental education, it is not possible for parents to fulfill their roles and duties in the family and society. Based on the four parenting styles-authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and uninvolved-one may be able to address the positive and negative behaviors associated with each parenting style. Little research has been done to further connect the two variables, and by conducting this research, the correlation between parenting styles and the academic performance of Grade 1 pupils could be determined. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to describe the extent to which parenting styles influence the academic performance of Grade 1 pupils, so that when results show adverse influence, actions can be proposed to alter the parenting styles of parents.

Parent involvement in a child's early education is consistently found to be positively associated with a child's academic performance (Hara & Burke, 1998; Hill & Craft, 2003; Marcon, 1999; Stevenson & Baker, 1987). Specifically, children whose parents are more involved in their education have higher levels of academic performance than children whose parents are involved to a lesser degree. The influence of parent involvement on academic success has not only been noted among researchers but also among policymakers who have integrated efforts aimed at increasing parent involvement into broader educational policy initiatives.

Similarly, the Philippine Department of Education introduced several programs to increase parental involvement in the educational process, such as the E-Learning Program, which brought together teachers, parents, and community members and gave them access to social media platforms and websites to track their children's progress (Abulon et al., 2016). Parents are the children's first teachers. They set the rules, guide the children, and provide for their necessities. Parents want their children to be successful in life, which is why they are always encouraging them. According to Garcia and Thornton (2014), parental involvement in learning benefits student achievement. It boosts their confidence, reduces absenteeism, and makes them more engaged in class. With correct instruction, children can achieve high scores, develop their social skills, and improve their behavior. In the community, this is a necessity because it reduces some undesirable behaviors like crime and poverty. The population is rising due to a lack of parental guidance, as is evident today. Because parents never check or monitor them, many

students drop out of school. Learners, according to Clinton and Hattie (2013), obtain knowledge not just in school but also at home.

It is on this note that the researcher thought of conducting this research since it is timely. Thus, the results and findings of this present study served as a basis for contextualizing a partnership program on Parenting Style and Parenting Involvement.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the parenting styles and parental environmental of Grade 1 learners' parents in selected elementary schools of Amulung West District, as a basis for partnership program for the School Year 2024-2025.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Marital Status
 - 1.3 Occupation
 - 1.4 Highest Education Attainment
 - 1.5 Gross Monthly Income
 - 1.6 Educational Resources available at home
2. What is the parenting style of the respondents?
3. What is the level of parental involvement of the respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1 Parenting
 - 3.2 Communicating
 - 3.3 Volunteering
 - 3.4 Learning at Home
 - 3.5 Decision-making
 - 3.6 Collaborative with the community
4. What is the academic performance of the learners?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the parenting styles of the respondents and their profile variables?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the parental involvement of the respondents in their profile variables?
7. Is there significant relationship between the parenting styles of the respondents and the academic performance of the learners?
8. Is there a significant relationship on the parental involvement of respondents and the academic performance of the learners?
9. What are the issues and concerns encountered by the respondents?
10. What partnership program can be proposed to address the issues and concerns encountered by the respondents?

II. METHODS and PROCEDURES

Research Design

The study used a descriptive-correlational research design, as it described the respondents' profile, parenting styles, parent involvement of the learners' parents/guardians, and their academic performance. The descriptive design was employed to determine the profile of the respondents and documented the learners' academic performance. The study also utilized correlational analysis to examine the relationships between parenting styles and parent involvement across different schools. Furthermore, the correlational design was used to determine the significance of parenting styles and parent involvement on learners' academic performance and to assess whether the profile variables of the parents/guardians influenced their parenting styles and level of involvement.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the parents of Grade 1 learners from selected elementary schools in West Amulung District, Cagayan. Total enumeration was used; however, only those who gave their consent were included in the study. Hence, their participation was voluntary.

Table 1

Distribution of the Respondents of the Study

School	Parents
San Juan Elementary School	23
Casingsingan Sur Elementary School	14
Cordova Elementary School	29
Annafatan Elementary School	24
Nabbialan Elementary School	17
Nangalasaunan Elementary School	28
Total	135

Data Gathering Tool

The instrument on data-gathering used in this study was a questionnaire, which was answered by 135 parents/guardians in the selected elementary schools of the West Amulung District.

Part I was on the Personal Profile Questionnaire, which involved information on the profile of the parent/guardian respondents in terms of age, civil status, highest educational attainment, occupation, gross monthly income, and educational resources available at home.

Part II was the parenting style questionnaire entitled "What's Your Parenting Style," which was adopted from Joan E. Le Febvre, a professor in the Department of Family Development. The instrument has been utilized for various purposes. This questionnaire is

a reliable depiction of how each parent rates themselves as parents from a series of always (3), sometimes (2), and never (1). Sixteen questions are categorized into different types of parenting styles.

Items	3,	7,	9,	and 10	fall	under the authoritative style;
Items	2,	8,	12,	and 14	fall	under the authoritarian style;
Items	1,	11,	13,	and 15	fall	under the permissive style; and
Items	4	5	6	and 16	fall	under the unengaged style.

Part III was the parental involvement questionnaire, and Part IV was the challenges faced by the parents, which was developed by Joyce Epstein and her colleagues. They created a suitable structure of six categories of parental involvement, containing parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and collaborating with the community (Peiffer, 2015). The authors note that the Framework of Six Types of Involvement is intended to support the development and implementation of a systemic approach to partnerships, ideally one that cultivates a “culture of partnerships” throughout a district or school.

Part V was the collection of the general average of the learners from their respective advisers.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following steps were followed in gathering the data in pursuit of this study:

First, the researcher secured an Ethics Clearance from the Institutional Review Board of the university, which guaranteed that the questionnaires to be used followed the ethical standards and procedures of research. Then, the researcher prepared a communication letter to request permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study. She also sought permission from the district supervisor and all the school heads of the said district.

Upon approval, the researcher personally administered the consent forms and questionnaires to the parent respondents to ensure 100% retrieval of the questionnaires. The respondents answered the questionnaire to the best of their ability. The researcher translated and explained the questions to those who needed clearer explanations and understanding. The questionnaires were collected as soon as the respondents completed them.

The responses gathered from all the parents/guardians and teachers were collated, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted with the support of her statistician.

Statistical Tools

The study utilized the following statistical tools necessary for analyzing and interpreting the data gathered:

Frequency and percentage were used to determine the profile of the respondents.

Weighted mean was employed and interpreted in the parenting styles manifested by the parent/guardian of the learners using the modified 3-point scale below.

Scale	Range	Description
3	2.34-3.00	Always
2	1.67-2.33	Sometimes
1	1.00-1.66	Never

Furthermore, the weighted mean was utilized to determine the extent of parental involvement of the respondents using the scale below:

Scale	Ranges	Description
4	3.25-4.00	Always
3	2.50-3.24	Sometimes
2	1.75-2.49	Seldom
1	1.00-1.74	Never

To describe the academic performance of the learners the weighted mean was used to further analyze the data using the scale on below.

Descriptor	Grading Scale	Remarks
Outstanding	90 and above	Passed
Very Satisfactory	85-89	Passed
Satisfactory	80-84	Passed
Fairly Satisfactory	75-79	Passed
Did not meet Expectations	75 and below	Passed

Chi-Square was used to test the relationship between the parents' profile variables and the extent of their involvement, also in correlating the level of parental involvement and the academic performance of the learners.

Weighted Mean was used to determine how often the respondents encounter issues and concerns in their parenting using the scale below:

Scale	Ranges	Description
4	3.25-4.00	Always
3	2.50-3.24	Sometimes
2	1.75-2.49	Seldom
1	1.00-1.74	Never

III. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

In the light of the results and discussions, the following are the key findings of the study:

1. Profile of the Respondents

- Most of the Respondents are belong to age range 26-30 years old, married high school graduates, laborer, and have a monthly income range below 5,000.00. Also, learners use smartphones as the educational resources available at their home.

2. Parenting of the Respondents

- Majority of respondents prefer an authoritative parenting style

3. Level of Parental Involvement of the Respondents

Parenting

- Parents are always involved in terms of parenting

Communicating

- Parents are always involved in terms of communicating

Volunteering

- Parents are always involved in terms of volunteering

Learning at Home

- Parents are always involved in terms of learning at home

Decision-making

- Parents are always involved in terms decision- making

Collaborating with the community

- Parents are always involved in terms of collaborating with the Community

4. Academic Performance of the Learners

- Most of the learners have an average between 90 and 100 translating to outstanding

5. Correlation between the parenting styles of the respondents and their profile variables

- Only age, civil status, and highest educational attainment are significantly correlated with parenting styles

6. Correlation between the parental involvement of the respondents and their profile variables
 - In terms of Marital Status, only decision- making is significantly correlated, indicating that a parent's marital status directly affects their involvement in making decisions concerning their children's education.
 - In terms of Occupation, communication is significantly correlated, meaning that a parent's occupation influences their ability to communicate effectively, likely due to time and availability constraints.
 - The other variables-Age, Highest Educational Attainment, Gross Monthly Income, and Educational Resources-show no significant correlation with any indicators of parental involvement.
7. Correlation between the parenting styles of the respondents and the academic performance of the learners
 - Parenting style is correlated with the learner's academic performance.
8. Correlation on the parental involvement of respondents and the academic performance of the learners
 - None among the indicators of parental involvement is significantly correlated with the learners' academic performance
9. Issues and concerns encountered by the respondents
 - Parents seldom encounter issues and concerns on parenting

IV. CONCLUSIONS and RECOMMENDATION

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that the authoritative parenting style is the most preferred among millennials. It also highlights the importance of parental involvement in their children's educational pursuits. Children are more likely to be motivated, perform better academically, and develop stronger social skills when their parents actively participate in their education through open communication, involvement in school events, and support for learning at home.

Volunteering and learning at home have never been an issue for parents. Learning at home allows parents to support their children's education in flexible ways, such as helping with homework, encouraging reading habits, or providing a structured study environment-activities that do not require school intervention or external participation.

Decision-making, communication, and collaboration with the community are seldom challenges for parents in terms of involvement, as these aspects are often facilitated by schools and community organizations, making it easier for parents to engage. Schools actively encourage parental input in decision-making through parent-teacher associations, meetings, and surveys, ensuring that parents have a voice in educational policies and programs. Effective communication channels-such as newsletters, emails, and parent-teacher conferences-keep parents informed and engaged, reducing the likelihood of misunderstandings or disconnection.

This study further posits that parental involvement is vital in promoting harmony between families and the schools where their children are enrolled.

Recommendations

Derived from the substantial findings and conclusions of this study, the researcher advocates the following recommendations:

1. Despite the high level of parental involvement, it is recommended to school heads to establish a structured partnership program aimed at enhancing mutual understanding between teachers and parents regarding their respective roles in supporting children's academic achievement and overall morale.
2. Teachers may craft programs that would directly involve parents and their children such as family days to foster a harmonious relationship between the pupil, the parent, and the school.

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